

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Sirojiddinova O'g'ilo

AMIR XUDOYBERDI G'AZALLARIDA MUBOLAG'A SAN'ATI

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/FEVRAL

